

MASTERADIO: A TOOL TOWARDS PUPILS' PROFICIENCY ON BASIC MATHEMATICS

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Masteradio: A Tool Towards Pupils' Proficiency on Basic Mathematics

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of “MasterRadio” as a tool in increasing the proficiency level on basic operations among grade three pupils of J.M. Reliquias Elementary School in the District of Hinoba-an 1, for School Year 2022-2023. The researcher used a combination of single-subject experimental research design. It utilized weighted mean and mean percentage score in its treatment and computation of statistical data. Pre- and post-assessment scheme were also employed. The researcher made use of the Enhanced Regional Unified Numeracy Test (E-RUNT), as a standardized tool to determine the proficiency level of the pupils. The following were the salient findings of the study: 1) the Grade III pre-assessment results revealed “Nearly Proficient” with an MPS of 67.9; 2) after the 10-week implementation of the intervention MasteRadio, the post- assessment results yielded an MPS of 91.88 or “Highly Proficient”; 3) an increase of 23.98 in the post-assessment strongly indicated that the intervention “MasteRadio” was effective in increasing the grade III learners’ numeracy skill; 4) as to the remarkable experiences during and after the implementation of the “MasteRadio”, pupils found this intervention as an enjoyable activity in mastering basic operations; and 5) parents, were able to become motivated in facilitating and supervising their children in their learning. Thus, enabling them to realize the significant role they play in their children’s education and future.

Keywords: *basic operations, proficiency level, numeracy skill, E-RUNT, pre-assessment, post-assessment*

Introduction

Numeracy skills refer to the ability to use, interpret and communicate mathematical information to solve real world problems. However, to maximize this skill, one should possess understanding on basic math like addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. Guhl (2019) stated the importance of developing early math and numeracy skills as they are two of the many predictors in the learner’s academic success.

Undeniably, Philippines has been in the limelight in the previous year for garnering the lowest rank in terms of numeracy assessment result. In the report submitted by PISA (2018), the Philippines is among the countries which had the poor numerical competence. This data clearly implies that the mathematical abilities are poor in the Philippines. Layug et al (2021) revealed that learners’ attitude towards the subject, poor study habits, poor parental supervision or the excessive utilization of technologies might be the explanation for their continued underperformance in mathematics.

The same scenario is also happening in J.M. Reliquias Elementary School. In the previous consolidated Numeracy Assessment Report, it showed that among all grades, Grade III obtained the lowest percentage mean score of 35.23 and 37.88 in the multiplication and division operation, respectively. Likewise, the result of Enhanced Regional Unified Numeracy Test (E-RUNT) conducted in the fourth quarter school year 2021-2022 also showed a low percentage score in the same operations with 8 out 22 pupils were noted as non-numerates. With this alarming data, the school designed an intervention that can help in mitigating and even eliminating the said problem. One of the suggested solutions that the school implemented was the intervention called “MasteRadio”.

“MasteRadio” came from two words; “master” and “radio” which means mastery through the help of radio transistor. “MasteRadio” then, was an intervention which utilized audio recordings of basic facts saved in a flash drive and played using radio. This intervention was conducted among Grade 3 pupils as remedial intervention to enhance their mathematical skills especially in the multiplication and division operations.

Intervention

The tool aided in dealing with the low mastery level in basic mathematics of the Grade 3 learners. Transistor Radios with the flash drive containing recorded audios of basic mathematical facts and spencer cards were given to pupils.

The following were the procedures and steps in conduct “MasteRadio” as an intervention to pupil’s proficiency in basic mathematical operations:

1. Identification of the Problem: The teacher conducted E-RUNT pre-assessment. The teacher checked the answers and recorded the results. The teacher found out that the mastery or proficiency level of the pupils was very low. The teacher then designed an intervention to address the said problem.
2. Designing an Intervention: After the problem has been identified, the teacher designed an intervention “MasteRadio”. The “MasterRadio” served as a tool in improving pupils’ proficiency on basic mathematical operations. A recorded audio on basic facts involving the four (4) operations were recorded and saved in a flash drive and this was played by the pupils at home using a transistor radio. The instructions and explanations on how to use the said device were already discussed during the Homeroom PTA meeting.

Parents were oriented and given hard copies of procedures and steps in using the said device. The recorded audio and materials were prepared by the teacher himself.

Hereunder were the teacher's daily suggested activities in a week.

Table 1. Suggested activities for Teacher in the "MasteRadio" intervention

<i>Days</i>	<i>Activities</i>
Monday	Preparation of the material; spencer cards, transistors radio and flash drives.
Tuesday	Audio recording started.
Wednesday	Saving of audio recordings into the flash drives.
Thursday	Printing of hard copies of the spencer cards.
Friday	Distribution of the device to the pupils.

Aside from the audio recordings saved in the flash drives, the pupils were also given hard copies of materials that already had answers provided. The content of the audio recordings could also be found in the hard copies. Both the audio recordings and hard copies were divided into three parts. Part 1 focused on familiarizing and memorizing basic facts, Part 2 involved fill in the blanks, and Part 3 included simple word problems related to the four operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division).

The implementation of the intervention lasted for ten weeks or two and a half months. The intervention began after the problem was identified. Before implementing the intervention, the researcher conducted a pre-assessment test to evaluate the numeracy level of the pupils. After obtaining the results and confirming the need for intervention, the researcher proceeded with the implementation. The devices were distributed to the parents.

Below is the table outlining the suggested activities for learners during the "MasteRadio" intervention:

Table 2. Suggested activities for learners in the "MasteRadio" intervention

<i>Week</i>	<i>Activities</i>
1	Full listening, familiarization, and memorization of the basic facts.
2	Full listening coupled with writing the equation and the answers.
3	Full listening and giving of answers independently.
4	Full listening, writing the correct number sentences and giving of the correct answers.
5	In person assessment (done by the teacher in the classroom)

Weeks 1 to 4 involved home learning activities, while Week 5 consisted of an in-person assessment. In addition to the weekly tasks, the learners were also assessed every Friday based on the suggested activities for the week. The in-person assessment was conducted by the teacher and focused on two operations. Week 5 assessed addition and subtraction, while Week 10 assessed multiplication and division.

The evaluation and assessment of the intervention were conducted on a weekly basis. At the end of each week, an assessment was carried out based on the suggested activities. For example, if the activity for a particular week involved listening and memorization of basic facts, it was expected that the learners would demonstrate proficiency in listening and memorizing the facts from the audio recordings. This assessment continued throughout the weeks.

After the implementation of the intervention, a post-assessment was conducted by the researcher. The post-assessment included two forms: one focused on basic facts and the other on solving word problems involving the two operations. The post-assessment was done in-person and had a time limit. The scores were checked, tallied, and analyzed.

Action Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of "MasteRadio" as a tool to enhance the mastery of basic mathematics among Grade three pupils of J.M. Reliquias Elementary School in the District of Hinoba-an 1, for the School Year 2022-2023. The research aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the proficiency level of Grade three pupils in the four basic operations before and after the intervention?
2. Is there a difference in the proficiency level of Grade three pupils in the four basic operations before and after the intervention?
3. What are the notable experiences of the learners during and after the implementation of the "MasteRadio" intervention program?
4. What actions should be taken after the implementation of the intervention?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed an action research design. This pre-experimental research design was intended to determine the effectiveness of a treatment to a single group through a pre- and post-assessment scheme. Hence, in this study, MasteRadio was a treatment intended for a single group of 22 Grade 3 pupils of J.M. Reliquias Elementary School in the District of Hinoba-an I, Province of Negros

Occidental. Pre- and post-assessments, meanwhile, involved the participants' numeracy/mastery skill.

Participants

The participants of the study were the twenty-two (22) Grade 3 pupils of J.M. Reliquias Elementary School for school year 2022-2023. They were selected since they were under the direct supervisory of the researcher. Finally, they were selected based on complete enumeration. These pupils were the previous Grade 2 pupils in which low result in numeracy assessment was obtained.

Procedure

At the start of the first quarter, the teacher started the distribution of the radio devices and print out copies of the numeracy materials. In-person assessment was done on a weekly basis. In the 11th week, post-assessment conducted. The results of this assessment were checked, recorded, and analyzed. Lastly, the pre-assessment and the post-assessment results were compared to check whether there was an increase in the pupil's numeracy level after the implementation of the MasteRadio.

Data Analysis

For the researcher to determine the mastery/proficiency level of Grade 3 pupils in four (4) basic operations before and after the intervention program, weighted mean and mean percentage were used. The table below was used by the researcher in determining the proficiency level. (DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2022)

Table 3.

<i>Levels of Proficiency</i>	<i>Mean Percentage Score (MPS)</i>
Highly Proficient	90-100
Proficient	75-89
Nearly Proficient	50-74
Low Proficiency	25-49
Not Proficient	0-24

To determine the difference on the proficiency level of Grade 3 pupils in the four basic operations before and after the intervention program, the researcher subtracted the post-assessment results from the pre-assessment results. If there is an increase noted after the post-assessment result was being subtracted from the pre-assessment, then the intervention will be considered effective and beneficial.

For the identification of the remarkable experiences of the learners and parents during and after the implementation of the intervention, and the actions to be taken after the implementation of the intervention program, informal interview was employed through Thematic Analysis.

Results and Discussion

The analysis and interpretation of data based on results of the research study are presented below. Reflection, on the other hand, is presented hereafter.

1. Findings on the Mastery level of Grade three pupils in four (4) basic operations before and after the intervention:

Table 4 below shows the proficiency level of Grade III pupils in four basic operations before and after the implementation of MasteRadio as an intervention. It can be seen from the table that the proficiency level of pupils in four (4) basic operations during the pre-assessment is 'nearly proficient' with an MPS 67.9. However, after the implementation of the intervention MasteRadio, it yielded to 91.88 MPS which is 'Highly Proficient'. With this result, it can be inferred that MasteRadio as an intervention to pupils' mastery or proficiency of basic operation is effective.

In the article published by University of Maryland Medical Center (2013), students who receive audible instructions perform better in their learning since they pay attention which resulted in a better understanding of the directions. The same is true with this intervention, for the pupils to solve each question correctly, they need to listen and understand the audio recordings being played on the radio. If they failed to hear the directions given, they may play it again and again until they can fully understand it.

Table 4. *Mastery level of pupils before and After the Intervention*

<i>Mastery Level</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Before	67.9	Nearly Proficient
After	91.88	Highly Proficient

2. Findings on the difference on the proficiency level of Grade 3 pupils in four (4) basic operations before and after the intervention program:

Table 3 displays the difference in the mastery/proficiency level of pupils before and after the intervention. Based on the table, an increase of 23.93% is established after the conduct of the MasteRadio as an intervention to pupils' mastery or proficiency in the four basic operations. This further implies that MasteRadio is effective in increasing pupils' mastery level, thus transforming non-numerates into numerates after its implementation.

Table 5. *Difference on the Mastery Level of pupils before and after the Intervention*

		Mean	
Before	After	Result	Remarks
67.9	91.88	23.98	Increase

3. Remarkable experiences of pupils during the implementation of the intervention program, 'MasteRadio'.

This section discusses the remarkable experiences of the pupils and parents in the implementation of the intervention program. From the interview transcripts of the pupils and parents, the following (2) issues emerged:

A. Pupils: Mastering basic operations became easier and enjoyable with MasteRadio.

Mastering basic operations became easier and enjoyable with MasteRadio. Based on the findings, MasteRadio is an effective intervention in increasing the mastery level of Grade III pupils in four (4) basic operations. According to the pupils, they find their Mathematics lesson easier because they can easily master the multiplication table by listening to the audio recordings again and again until they memorized it.

B. Parents: Parents were motivated to facilitate and supervise their children's learning. They also realized the important role they play in their children's education.

Parents are the children's foremost teacher. Just like professional teachers, for the parents to fully supervised their children's learning, they also need facilities or materials. MasteRadio is indeed an ideal intervention which boosted parent's confidence to supervise their children's learning knowing that the materials are readily available and the procedures/steps in the implementation of the intervention were properly laid out.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher drawn the following conclusions: MasteRadio is effective in increasing pupil's mastery level in four (4) basic operations. Employment of different interventions is way better than plainly discussing the lesson in the classroom. Parental role and involvement in child's education can impact pupil's learning.

From the extensive analysis of data to the drawing of conclusions from the findings, the following are hereby recommended: Teachers handling Mathematics subject should consider the use of MasteRadio as an intervention in teaching pupil's numeracy skills. Parents should realize that parenting is not only in providing material needs of their children but also in helping them develop mentally, socially, emotionally, and spiritually. This means that their engagement in the education of their children can greatly contribute to their children's learning performance. The school should look for donors or benefactors that will help in the procurement and maintenance of instructional materials like radios or even Television sets.

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